

“Strategic Planning for Non Government Organizations in Sri Lanka – An Evaluation using the Balanced Scorecard”

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Abstract

The relationship between strategic planning and organizational performance has been examined in the nongovernment sectors. Moreover, most of the existing research has been confined to examining the nongovernment sector in the developing countries and very little has been conducted in developing countries. This study empirically examines the effect of strategic planning on Sri Lankan non government organization's performance effectiveness. An assessment of performance effectiveness was made using the multiple perspectives of the balanced scorecard (Robert S. Kaplan & David P. Norton, 2001). A fifth dimension was added to the balanced scorecard, developed originally by Niven (2008), which is volunteers' development. The research design was used to compare the performance of strategic planning non government versus that of non strategic planning non government. Random samples of 303 non government organizations were selected for study and 606 executive manager's participation in the study. Results have indicated a statistically significant difference between the mean composite scores of strategic planning activities in strategic versus non-strategic planning non governments along four out of five domains of the BSC performance effectiveness scale. These domains were namely; customer processes, internal business processes, employees learning and growth, volunteers' development except for financial processes. Results however, did not show that most of the Sri Lankan non governments are fully aware of the BSC as a tool for assessing their performance effectiveness.

Key Words: Balanced Scorecard (BSC); Non Government Organization's (NGO's); Strategic Planning (SP), Organizational Performance Effectiveness (OPE)

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Defining Strategic Planning

Bryson (1995) defined strategic planning as a “disciplined effort to produce fundamental decisions and actions that shape and guide what an organization (or other entity) is, what it does, and why it does it”. Bryson (1995) viewed strategic planning as the “process of determining what an organization intends to be in the future and how it will get there”. Pfeiffer, Goodstein, and Nolan (1986) viewed such planning as the “process by which the guiding members of an organization envision its future and develop the necessary procedures and operations to achieve that future”. In these definitions, as well as those offered by other authors, strategic planning has been viewed as a process of developing and maintaining a strategic fit among the mission of the organization, the strengths and weaknesses of the organization, and opportunities and challenges in the organization's external environment.

Some authors have distinguished between strategic planning and more-traditional long-range planning. Bryson (1995) suggested that this distinction results from strategic planning's focus on identifying and resolving issues, emphasis on assessment of environmental factors, development of an idealized version of an organization's future, and design of an action-oriented plan through consideration of a range of possible future directions.

According to the Balanced Scorecard Institute, the Strategic planning is an organizational management activity that is used to set priorities, focus energy and resources, strengthen operations, ensure that employees and other stakeholders are working toward common goals, establish agreement around intended outcomes/results, and assess and adjust the organization's direction in response to a changing environment. It is a disciplined effort that produces fundamental decisions and actions that shape and guide what an organization is, who it serves, what it does, and why it does it, with a focus on the future. Effective strategic planning articulates not only where an organization is going and the actions needed to make progress, but also how it will know if it is successful.

1.2. Non Government Organization and Strategic Planning

Verschuere.B & Corte.J.D. (2014) identified that the non government organizations (NGO's) involved in publically funded welfare programs face the challenge of maintaining autonomy in their strategic decision-making processes. The extent to which NGO's managers perceive this autonomy vis-à-vis government in defining the NGO's mission, their working procedures, the target groups to be served and the results to be achieved. Empirical evidence is taken from a large sample of 255 NGOs engaged in social welfare provision in Belgium. The findings suggest that public resource dependence does have a negative impact on the perception of NGO's about the level of organizational autonomy. When looking at the relative share of public income in the NGO's total budget, the nature and intensity of the consultation process between government and NGO and some measures of organizational capacity, this picture is

less black and white than presumed.

Ghoneim.N.A. 2012 describe strategic planning can help organizations develop strategic thinking and adapt to environmental changes; non government organizations may run into challenges when using strategic planning in their management practice. Strategic planning can be time-consuming and cost extra human capital and monetary resources that many non government organizations have limited access to. Hence, it is worthwhile to examine the application of strategic planning and management to non government organizations and evaluate the benefits and challenges that strategic planning can bring to non governments.

Mohammed Mouadili (2015) pointed out that the growth and rapid spread of non-governmental organizations in many regions, dealing and managing these organizations turned to be a big challenge. One of the approaches that non-governmental organizations have to rely on is strategic management. By acting strategically, these organizations can promote their capabilities and keep their obligations toward communities.

Naim Kapucu & Lauren O'Byrne, (2014) describe strategic planning can help organizations develop strategic thinking and adapt to environmental changes; non government organizations may run into challenges when using strategic planning in their management practice. Strategic planning can be time-consuming and cost extra human capital and monetary resources that many non government organizations have limited access to. Hence, it is worthwhile to examine the application of strategic planning and management to non government organizations and evaluate the benefits and challenges that strategic planning can bring to non governments.

Franklin.P.W.(2011) asserted that strategic planning is a critical part of the strategic management process which helps non government organizations formulate and realize strategies aimed at greater performance effectiveness, improved accountability measures, and sustainable competitive advantage (Jansen et al., 2006). Therefore, they need to adopt formal strategic planning aspects into their operations. Strategic planning is an integral part of organizational process (Kriemadis and Theakou, 2007). They argue that strategy has been used in the very early history and can be traced back to the military. The notion has been widely spread to the for profit sector. Bryson (1995) mentioned that this thought has been also transferred to the non government sector to enable organizations to adapt effectively to the highly competitive environment which is full with comparators rather than competitors as is the situation in the for profit sector.

1.3. Non Government organization and Balanced Scorecard

Handoussa (2008), in Egypt human development report, 2008 concluded that the yardstick for non government organizations' success lies in the quality of their work not the quantity (as measured by their count). By quality means, relevance of activities to sector needs, operational efficiency, competence benchmarks, in addition to the practice of good governance. The researcher agrees with this contention in that effective non government organizations have to manage their performance with regard to the dimensions Handoussa (2008) referred to which are more relevant to the multiple dimensions of performance measurement presented by the balanced scorecard (as a composite indicator of performance effectiveness).

The balanced scorecard allows non government organizations to include multiple indicators to measure their performance (Stone, Bigelow, and Crittenden, 1999). It can therefore add more consistency and flexibility to non government strategic planning efforts. This is because it considers resource allocation decisions with strategy development, focuses on performance measurement from multiple perspectives, and offers an effective tool for monitoring non government's success (Munive-Hernandex et al., 2004).

1.4. Problem Statement

Little research has been directed toward examining how strategic planning can be used to improve non governments effectiveness using a multiple performance measurement tool like the balanced scorecard especially in the third world developing countries (Blackmon, 2008; Franklin, 2011; and Kaissi, Begun, and Nelson, 2008) like Sri Lanka. According to the study the non government organizations play a central role in society by addressing key social problems through community and public services. In addition to significant number of respondents expressed dissatisfaction regarding the implementation of performance development and strategic planning process (N. Agilan, B.A.N. Eranda, 2011 and Ghoneim, 2012).

Organizational performance is described as an organization's ability to acquire and utilize its scarce resources and valuables as expeditiously as possible in the pursuit of its operations goals (Griffins, 2006). Several studies have been

conducted on the relationship between strategic planning and organizational performance in Non-Governmental Organizations. Ramanand.M. (2015) and Muturia (2009) studied multi-dimensional strategic planning practices and firm performance. Ong'ayo (2012) carried out research on employee perception of the influence of strategic planning on organization performance.

This study therefore was meant to establish the relationship between strategic planning and organization's performance in Non-Governmental Organizations in Sri Lanka. Therefore this clearly indicated that no study had been undertaken on the relationship of strategic planning to organization's performance in NGOs in Sri Lanka and performance measurement using the Balanced Scorecard. The knowledge gap necessitated this research study conducted on strategic planning factors and choices that influence organization's performance in non-governmental Organizations and in particular Action Aid Sri Lanka. **The current research attempts to fill in this gap by studying how strategic planning can be used as means for improving organizations performance effectiveness in non governments operating in Sri Lanka using the balanced scorecard.**

1.5. Research Questions

The current research focuses to answer the following questions;

1. What is the relationship between strategic planning and performance effectiveness as measured by mission achievement in Sri Lankan non government organizations?
2. What is the relationship between customer perspective and performance effectiveness in non government organizations in Sri Lanka?
3. What is the relationship between internal business processes and performance effectiveness in non government organizations in Sri Lanka?
4. What is the relationship between employees' learning and growth and performance effectiveness in non government organizations in Sri Lanka?
5. What is the relationship between financial processes and performance effectiveness in non government organizations in Sri Lanka?
6. What is the relationship between volunteers' development and performance effectiveness in non government organizations in Sri Lanka?

1.6. Research Objectives

The current research focuses to achieve the following objectives;

1. To examine the relationship between strategic planning and organizational performance effectiveness in non government organizations in Sri Lanka.
2. To study the relationship between mission achievement and organizational performance effectiveness in non government organizations in Sri Lanka.
3. To analysis the relationship between perspectives in balanced (customer, internal business processes, employees' learning and growth, financial processes, and volunteers' development) and organizational performance effectiveness in non government organizations in Sri Lanka.

1.7. Non Government Organization in Sri Lanka

The Non Government Organizations (NGOs) play an important role in the socioeconomic process of the countries in which they operate. This is true not only in developing countries, but also in developed countries. NGOs in Sri Lanka are no exception. These organizations are important players in both the social and political spheres. The first activities in Sri Lanka, similar to those of an NGO emerged during the British colonial period in the late 19th century. About 100 years later, with the macro changes in the country, a substantial expansion of NGO presence in Sri Lanka took place. A considerable sum of funds, received from both national and international sources is handled by these NGOs. This situation has been further enhanced by the Tsunami of 26th December 2004, which resulted in an unprecedented inflow of financial and other resources in to the country and the formation or representation in Sri Lanka of many more such organizations.

The non government sector in Sri Lanka is mostly highly fragmented and ignores the formal aspects of strategic planning practices. This might be due to their belief that they do not possess enough resources to enable them to engage in formal strategic planning processes.

METHODOLOGY

The current study attempted to empirically examine the effect of strategic planning on non government organization's performance effectiveness. An assessment of performance effectiveness was made using the multiple perspectives of

performance assessment offered by the modified balanced scorecard tool. The balanced scorecard organizational effectiveness scale measured the organizational outcomes, as captured by organizational change, along five major perspectives (customer processes, internal business processes, employees' learning and growth, financial processes, and volunteers' development) for non governments that apply formal strategic planning protocols. On the other hand, organizational change was measured for the last operating years as respondents were instructed in the questionnaire.

2.1. Research Framework

The researcher relied on the empirical model proposed by Blackmon (2008) to measure the relationship between strategic planning and performance effectiveness in Sri Lankan non government organizations using the balanced scorecard approach. A retrospective survey instrument, based on the efforts of Blackmon (2008), was adopted and modified to measure the proposed relationships among research constructs. Franklin (2011) and Ghoneim (2012) were applied to the dimensions of performance assessment offered by the balanced scorecard after modification. A fifth dimension which is volunteers' development was added to the four dimensions of the balanced scorecard (customer processes, internal business processes, employee learning and growth, financial processes). This was due to researcher's belief that volunteers have an important role in the work of non governments in Sri Lanka. Hence, the researcher has developed a scale, composed of six items, to measure volunteers' development and it was incorporated into the original BSC performance effectiveness scale. Therefore, the current research model is considered as an extension to the model developed earlier by Blackmon (2008) that has been modified to fit application into the different context within which non governments operate in Sri Lanka. The research model is shown in the following figure.

Figure 1.1 – Research Model

2.2. Research Hypotheses

Simple and multiple linear regression analysis were used to test research hypotheses. General organizational performance was the dependent variable as measured by the six domains of the BSC performance effectiveness scale. These domains are mission achievement, customer processes, internal business processes, employee learning and growth, financial processes, and volunteers' development. The organizational change scale captured information about these six domains to cross validate data obtained in earlier sections of the questionnaire. Multiple regression analysis was used to test research hypothesis using data collected from entirely completed questionnaires.

Hypothesis 1

There is a significant relationship between strategic planning and organizational performance in non government organizations.

Hypothesis 2

There is a significant relationship between mission achievement and organizational performance in non government organizations.

Hypothesis 3

There is a significant relationship between customer processes and organizational performance in non government

organizations.

Hypothesis 4

There is a significant relationship between internal business processes and organizational performance in non government organizations.

Hypothesis 5

There is a significant relationship between employee learning and growth and organizational performance in non government organizations.

Hypothesis 6

There is a significant relationship between financial processes and organizational performance in non government organizations.

Hypothesis 7

There is a significant relationship between volunteers' development and organizational performance in non government organizations.

2.3. Study population and sampling technique

The target population for the study was comprised of Sri Lankan non government organizations. There were 1397 registered NGO's operates in Sri Lanka (National Secretariat for Non Government Organizations). The probability sampling technique that can be used in quantitative research designs (Sekaran.U; Bougie. R. 2011 fifth edition: page 270). It allows the researcher to draw the sample that would best fit the research intended objectives (Dolores and Tongco, 2007). Therefore, a systematic sample of 303 non government organizations was selected out of 1397 non government organizations (Krejcie and Morgan 1970 – Generalized scientific guidelines for sample size decisions – Sekaran.U; Bougie. R. 2011 fifth edition: page 295 - Research Methods for Business: India: Wiley Publication) and sample which represented that the 25 districts in all over the country. In addition to randomly selected 560 senior executives (two questionnaires given to one particular organization) from the 303 non government organizations. The following few studies represent that the sample selections based on the population in the non government organization research studies.

Finally 560 questionnaires were distributed to employees, 475 questionnaires were returned. Thus 475 usable questionnaires were yielded which resulted in an 85% response rate across the 16 NGO's in Sri Lanka.

2.4. Data Analysis

Pilot Testing

Initially 25 NGO's selected and distributed 50 questionnaires to the participants for the pilot study, 50 responses were received (100% response rate for the pilot study).

According to the discussions focused on both the reliability and validity of the proposed items for the instruments. For this purpose 25 non government organizations (50 executives) were selected to collection of data. The analyses for the pilot study are as follows.

Table 2.1: Reliability results of the pilot study and the main study

Scale	Pilot study no of items	Cronbach's alpha	KMO for pilot study	Action taken	Main study no of items
Strategic planning process	8	0.928	0.865	1	7
Mission achievement	6	0.861	0.784	1	5
Customer perspective	7	0.909	0.679	1	6
Internal business process perspective	5	0.928	0.844	-	5
Employee learning and growth perspective	4	0.730	0.820	-	4
Financial perspective	3	0.816	0.722	-	3
Volunteer's development and	6	0.861	0.861	1	5
Organizational performance effectiveness	9	0.886	0.733	3	6

DATA ANALYSIS

3.1. Strategic Planning Process (S.P.P)

In strategic planning process, the KMO value is 0.879, which is considered excellent. If the KMO value is too low, check the anti-image correlation matrix. In this matrix, for a good factor analysis, the diagonal values must be close to 1 and the off diagonal element must be close to 0. If the initial KMO value is too low, seek improvement by dropping the variable that gives the smallest value along the diagonal.

Confirmatory factor analysis was used to examine the convergent validity of the items listed in the questionnaire. With respect to strategic planning, confirmatory factor analysis resulted in only one component. In the following, since there are 7 variables in this analysis, 7 components (or factors) are listed in the first column. The respective eigen values and percent of variance explained are provided in the next two columns. For Factor 1, the eigen value is 4.912. Since the total variance is 7, this works out to: $4.912/7 \times 100 = 70.176\%$ of the total variance. For factor 2, the eigen value is 0.775, less than the default value of 1. In the same table, under "Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings", only one factor is listed, corresponding to the factor for which the eigen values is more than 1. Based on the cumulative % column, this factor explains 70.176% of the total variance in the 7 original variables. All seven items measuring strategic planning were significant and had factor loadings above .5 and thus are considered practically significant (Hair, et al., 1998).

Table (4-1): Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Strategic Planning

Items	Components
	Factor
Our organization have followed strategic planning activities during the past years	.895
Our organization conducts strategic planning activities based on organizational goals	.825
Our strategic plan is developed based on internal and operational efficiency	.934
Our strategic plan will evaluate the external factors before implementation	.550
Our strategic planning process identifies the most critical issues faced by the organization	.948
Our organization sets specific activities to address each of these critical issues	.781
Our organization establishes the performance indicators to measure the achievement of goals in the strategic plan process	.864

3.2. Mission Achievement (M.A)

In mission achievement, the KMO value is 0.592, which is considered mediocre. In this matrix, for a good factor analysis, the diagonal values must be close to 1 and the off diagonal element must be close to 0. If the initial KMO value is too low, seek improvement by dropping the variable that gives the smallest value along the diagonal.

Confirmatory factor analysis was used to examine the convergent validity of the items listed in the questionnaire. With respect to mission achievement, confirmatory factor analysis resulted in only one component. In the following, since there are 5 variables in this analysis, 5 components (or factors) are listed in the first column. The respective eigen values and percent of variance explained are provided in the next two columns. For Factor 1, the eigen value is 2.694. Since the total variance is 5, this works out to: $2.694/5 \times 100 = 53.881\%$ of the total variance. For factor 2, the eigen value is 0.954, less than the default value of 1. In the same table, under “Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings”, only one factor is listed, corresponding to the factor for which the eigen values is more than 1. Based on the cumulative % column, this factor explains 53.881% of the total variance in the 5 original variables. All five items measuring mission achievement were significant and had factor loadings above .5 and thus are considered practically significant (Hair, et al., 1998).

Table (4-2): Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Mission Achievement

Items	Components
	Factor
Our organization mission is used to make rational decisions	.543
My profession helps to achieve our organization mission	.823
My day to day duties help to achieve our organization mission	.788
Our co-workers day to day duties help to achieve our organization mission	.760
Our organization consistently consider the achievement of our mission statement	.723

3.3. Customer Perspective (C.P)

In customer perspective, the KMO value is 0.699, which is considered acceptable. In this matrix, for a good factor analysis, the diagonal values must be close to 1 and the off diagonal element must be close to 0. If the initial KMO value is too low, seek improvement by dropping the variable that gives the smallest value along the diagonal.

Confirmatory factor analysis was used to examine the convergent validity of the items listed in the questionnaire. With respect to customer perspective, confirmatory factor analysis resulted in only one component. In the following, since

there are 5 variables in this analysis, 5 components (or factors) are listed in the first column. The respective Eigen values and percent of variance explained are provided in the next two columns. For Factor 1, the Eigen value is 3.243 since the total variance is 5, this works out to: $3.243/5 \times 100 = 64.853\%$ of the total variance. For factor 2, the Eigen value is 0.969, above the default value of 1. In the same table, under “Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings”, only one factor is listed, corresponding to the factor for which the Eigen values is more than 1. Based on the cumulative % column, this factor explains 64.853% of the total variance in the 5 original variables. All five items measuring customer perspective were significant and had factor loadings above .5 and thus are considered practically significant (Hair, et al., 1998).

Table (4-3): Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Customer Perspective

Items	Components
	Factor
We consistently meet the expectations of funding agencies	.853
We consistently meet the expectations of donors	.771
We consistently meet the expectations of our community	.891
The quality of the services we provide has been improved	.653
The type of services we provide has been improved	.837

3.4. Internal Business Process Perspective (I.B.P.P)

In internal business process perspective, the KMO value is 0.860, which is considered excellent. In this matrix, for a good factor analysis, the diagonal values must be close to 1 and the off diagonal element must be close to 0. If the initial KMO value is too low, seek improvement by dropping the variable that gives the smallest value along the diagonal.

Confirmatory factor analysis was used to examine the convergent validity of the items listed in the questionnaire. With respect to internal business process perspective, confirmatory factor analysis resulted in only one component. In the following, since there are 5 variables in this analysis, 5 components (or factors) are listed in the first column. The respective Eigen values and percent of variance explained are provided in the next two columns. For Factor 1, the Eigen value is 3.636 since the total variance is 5, this works out to: $3.636/5 \times 100 = 72.720\%$ of the total variance. For factor 2, the Eigen value is 0.708, below the default value of 1. In the same table, under “Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings”, only one factor is listed, corresponding to the factor for which the Eigen values is more than 1. Based on the cumulative % column, this factor explains 72.720% of the total variance in the 5 original variables. All five items measuring internal business process perspective were significant and had factor loadings above .5 and thus are considered practically significant (Hair, et al., 1998).

Table (4-4): Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Internal Business Process Perspective

Items	Components
	Factor
Our organization continuously improve the planning processes	.877
Our organization continuously provide the quality programming	.857
Our organization continuously improve the quality control processes	.937
Our organization continuously improve the service delivery processes	.611
Our organization continuously develop the policies and procedures	.939

3.5. Employee Learning and Growth Perspective (E.L.G.P)

In employee learning and growth perspective, the KMO value is 0.661, which is considered excellent. In this matrix,

for a good factor analysis, the diagonal values must be close to 1 and the off diagonal element must be close to 0. If the initial KMO value is too low, seek improvement by dropping the variable that gives the smallest value along the diagonal.

Confirmatory factor analysis was used to examine the convergent validity of the items listed in the questionnaire. With respect to employee learning and growth perspective, confirmatory factor analysis resulted in only one component. In the following, since there are 3 variables in this analysis, 4 components (or factors) are listed in the first column. The respective Eigen values and percent of variance explained are provided in the next two columns. For Factor 1, the Eigen value is 2.211 since the total variance is 4, this works out to: $2.211/3 \times 100 = 73.716\%$ of the total variance. For factor 2, the Eigen value is 0.556, below the default value of 1. In the same table, under “Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings”, only one factor is listed, corresponding to the factor for which the eigen values is more than 1. Based on the cumulative % column, this factor explains 73.716% of the total variance in the 3 original variables. All four items measuring employee learning and growth perspective were significant and had factor loadings above .5 and thus are considered practically significant (Hair, et al., 1998).

Table (4-5): Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Employee Learning and Growth Perspective

Items	Components
	Factor
My organization provides new challenges to develop employee work related skills	.774
I am satisfied with current reward and recognition system in organization	.911
I have received an enough information from my organization to meet the requirement for the particular task	.884

3.6. Financial Perspective (F.P)

In financial perspective, the KMO value is 0.653, which is considered good. In this matrix, for a good factor analysis, the diagonal values must be close to 1 and the off diagonal element must be close to 0. If the initial KMO value is too low, seek improvement by dropping the variable that gives the smallest value along the diagonal.

Confirmatory factor analysis was used to examine the convergent validity of the items listed in the questionnaire. With respect to financial perspective, confirmatory factor analysis resulted in only one component. In the following, since there are 3 variables in this analysis, 3 components (or factors) are listed in the first column. The respective eigen values and percent of variance explained are provided in the next two columns. For Factor 1, the eigen value is 2.132 since the total variance is 3, this works out to: $2.132/3 \times 100 = 71.053\%$ of the total variance. For factor 2, the eigen value is 0.605, below the default value of 1. In the same table, under “Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings”, only one factor is listed, corresponding to the factor for which the eigen values is more than 1. Based on the cumulative % column, this factor explains 71.053% of the total variance in the 3 original variables. All three items measuring financial perspective were significant and had factor loadings above .5 and thus are considered practically significant (Hair, et al., 1998).

Table (4-6): Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Financial Perspective

Items	Components
	Factor
I appear to be more valuable at cost control	.894
I appear to maintain low operating expense	.883
I appear to properly allot our financial resources through the programs	.744

3.7. Volunteers’ Development Perspective (V.D.P)

In volunteers’ development perspective, the KMO value is 0.671, which is considered excellent. In this matrix, for a good factor analysis, the diagonal values must be close to 1 and the off diagonal element must be close to 0. If the initial KMO value is too low, seek improvement by dropping the variable that gives the smallest value along the diagonal.

Confirmatory factor analysis was used to examine the convergent validity of the items listed in the questionnaire. With respect to volunteers' development perspective, confirmatory factor analysis resulted in only one component. In the following, since there are 3 variables in this analysis, 5 components (or factors) are listed in the first column. The respective eigen values and percent of variance explained are provided in the next two columns. For Factor 1, the eigen value is 2.284 since the total variance is 5, this works out to: $2.284/3 \times 100 = 76.124\%$ of the total variance. For factor 2, the eigen value is 0.525, below the default value of 1. In the same table, under "Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings", only one factor is listed, corresponding to the factor for which the eigen values is more than 1. All three items measuring volunteers' development perspective were significant and had factor loadings above .5 and thus are considered practically significant (Hair, et al., 1998).

Table (4-7): Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Volunteers' Development Perspective

Items	Components
	Factor
My organization nurtures an internal environment that allows volunteers to feel connected with the organization	.911
My organization has an efficient management system for volunteers	.785
My organization provides volunteers' support at all organizational levels	.915

3.8. Organizational Performance Effectiveness (O.P.E)

In organizational performance change, the KMO value is 0.766, which is considered good. In this matrix, for a good factor analysis, the diagonal values must be close to 1 and the off diagonal element must be close to 0. If the initial KMO value is too low, seek improvement by dropping the variable that gives the smallest value along the diagonal.

Confirmatory factor analysis was used to examine the convergent validity of the items listed in the questionnaire. With respect to organizational performance change, confirmatory factor analysis resulted in only one component. In the following, since there are 5 variables in this analysis, 6 components (or factors) are listed in the first column. The respective eigen values and percent of variance explained are provided in the next two columns. For Factor 1, the eigen value is 3.880 since the total variance is 6, this works out to: $3.880/5 \times 100 = 64.66\%$ of the total variance. For factor 2, the eigen value is 1.006, below the default value of 1. In the same table, under "Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings", only one factor is listed, corresponding to the factor for which the eigen values is more than 1. Based on the cumulative % column, this factor explains 64.66% of the total variance in the 5 original variables. All five items measuring Organizational Performance Change were significant and had factor loadings above .5 and thus are considered practically significant (Hair, et al., 1998).

Table (4-8): Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Organizational Performance Change

Items	Components
	Factor
Involvement of the management board is a key achievement in organizational performance	.802
The changes of employee morale, commitment, training, their educational level and individual contribution have been supported to overall changes in organizational performance	.738
The low level of employee turnover, higher team work and work climate help for the changes in work process	.906
Community support activities, programme expansion, quality of programme and changes in programme participants favorably effect to the organizational performance	.648
The changes in different sources of grants would help to better achievement of organizational performance	.863
The cooperate image and the reputation have been achieved through the staff, customer and Volunteer dedication	.840

Based on the tests of convergent validity, the independent variables are strategic planning, mission achievement, customer processes, internal business processes, employee learning and growth, financial processes, and volunteers' development. The dependent variable is general organizational change which captures changes in organizational performance effectiveness over the last operating years and cross validates information collected about the five domains of the BSC in earlier sections of the questionnaire.

3.9. Assessing the Reliability of Scale Items

Cronbach alpha coefficient was used to examine the reliability of research constructs. The procedure of calculating Cronbach alpha coefficients after item deletion was employed to improve the reliability of scale variables. The following table (4-9) summarizes the results of the internal reliability of research items.

Table (4-9): Reliability of Research Items

Construct	Cronbach alpha Coefficient
Strategic Planning Process	0.924
Mission Achievement	0.771
Customer Perspective	0.862
Internal Business Processes Perspective	0.900
Employee Learning and Growth Perspective	0.820
Financial Perspective	0.794
Volunteers' Development Perspective	0.842
Organizational Performance Effectiveness	0.887

The reliability analysis shows that Cronbach alpha coefficients for the variables strategic planning process, mission achievement, customer perspectives, internal business process perspectives, employee learning and growth perspective, financial perspective, volunteers' development perspective, and organizational performance change exceeded .8. Gliem and Gliem (2003) considered Cronbach alpha of greater than or equal .8 as a reasonable indicator of the internal consistency of scale items.

3.10. Discriminant Validity Tests

In order to test the discriminant validity of research variables, Cronbach alpha coefficient for each variable will be compared with its correlation with other variables (Sharma and Patterson, 1999). Independent research variables include strategic planning, mission achievement, customer processes, internal business processes, employee learning and growth, financial processes, and volunteers' development. Table (4-10) will present the correlation matrix of independent research variables with alpha coefficient for each variable.

Based on table (4-10) one type of comparison will be performed. This comparison will be between alpha coefficients for each variable and its correlation coefficients with all other variables. With respect to this type of comparison, significant correlations exist between most of the research variables, yet all of these correlations are lower than the alpha coefficients for each variable individually. For example, strategic planning and mission achievement are significantly correlated ($r = .746$) yet the reliability coefficients for both variables are .924 and .771 respectively, this means that respondents can discriminate between the two variables although they are correlated. This also means that for other research variables respondents can discriminate between different variables. Thus, the independent variables correlate at an appropriate level as shown by their respective correlation coefficients and at the reported significance levels also they are free from multicollinearity problems. But the I.B.P.P values are higher than the reliability values. Thus these variables are problem with multicollinearity.

- The r values between M.A and E.L.G.P, F.P, C.P and V.D.P values are less than 0.3. Thus there is a lower association between the variables.
- The r values between other variables are higher than 0.3. Thus there are strong associations between the variables.

3.11. Descriptive Characteristics of Respondent Non government Organizations

Based on table (4-11) and the analysis of the qualitative data, most of the organizations reported multiple service category provision. About 20.6 % of respondent organizations provided healthcare services. 47.5% provided both youth and educational services. 32.5% provided poverty alleviation services. 17.9% provided training and educational services. There are two services provided 6.1%, both environment and rehabilitation and re construction services. 17.3% reported a variety of other services including charity, economic and social development, elderly care, marketing and promotional services for businessmen, training and employment services, cultural exchange, funding projects, widows’ care and finally religious services.

Demographical data about the employee position in the organization, age group, gender, employee tenure in the organization and no of employee in the organization results are presented in the following table.

Table (4-12): Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Employee Position:		
President	4	0.8
General Secretary	7	1.5
Treasurer	8	1.7
Executive Director	34	7.2
Deputy Executive Director	166	34.9
Executive Assistant or Other Officer	256	53.9
Age Group:		
Less than 30 years	7	1.5
30-40 years	152	32.0
41-50 years	188	39.6
51-60 years	83	17.5
More than 60 years	45	9.5
Gender:		
Male	317	66.7
Female	158	33.3
Employee Tenure:		
Below 5	150	31.6
6 to 10	154	32.4
11- 15	134	28.2
More than 15	37	7.8
No of employee:		
Less than 25 employees	326	68.6
Between 26 and 50 employees	86	18.1
Between 51 and 75 employees	11	2.3
Between 76 and 100 employees	12	2.5
Over 100 employees	40	8.4

Based on table (4-12), majority of respondents (54%) indicated their position as the Executive Assistant or Other Officers. Deputy Executive Directors represented 35% of respondents, 7.2% were Executive Directors and 0.8% of respondents were President in the non government organizations.

Based on table (4-12), majority of respondents fell in the age bracket from 41 to 50 years old (39.6%). About 32% of respondents from 30 to 40, 17.5% represent the age group of 51 to 60 and above 60 years old age group represent 9.5%.

Based on table (4-12), 67% of respondents were male and only 33% were female. This highlights the fact the women are misrepresented in the management of non government organizations in Sri Lanka.

Based on table (4-12), majority of respondents spent from 6 to 10 years in tenure in their organizations (32.4%). 31.6% of respondents spent less than 5 years in tenure and they were mostly found in strategic planner organizations and also 28.2% respondents spent from 11 to 15. Finally, 7.8% spent more than 15 years in tenure. This is a good indicator about the adequacy of information reported by respondents based on their accumulated professional experience in the examined organizations.

In addition to the data presented above, categorical data about the size of respondent organizations in terms of the number of employees were collected and presented in the table 4-12. These categories are mutually exclusive. Based on table (4-12), 68.6% of respondent organizations operate a number of employees less than 25 employees. 18.1% operate within the employee group between 26 to 50 and 2.3% operate with a number of employees ranging from 51 to 75 employees.

3.12. Hypothesis Testing

3.12.1. Simple Linear Regression

3.12.1.1. Bivariate Analysis

The purpose of bivariate data analysis is to help to understand the association between two quantitative variables. This can be done by viewing the two variables in a scatter plot and quantifying the strength of association using correlation analysis. If an association can be established, both empirically and theoretically, the researcher may pursue to obtain a regression model to explain how a change in one variable affects the value on the other. The predictor variable is often called the independent variable and the predicted (or outcome) variable is often called the dependent variable. Usually alphabets X and Y are used to represent the independent and dependent variables, respectively.

3.12.1.2. Durbin-Watson statistics

The correlation among the residuals can also be quantified using the Durbin Watson (DW) statistics. The DW value ranges from 0 to 4, where values around 2 indicate no problem of autocorrelation. If the DW value is close to 0, there is a possibility of positive autocorrelation, the residuals increasing in value. When the DW value is close to 4, there is an indication of negative autocorrelation.

3.12.1.3. Test of normality

The regression procedure in SPSS provides an option to save the residuals values. Using this option, the residuals can be saved and test of normality can be performed on these saved values using the Explore procedure. If the p-value of the test is more than 0.05, normality of the residuals can be assumed.

H1: There is a significant relationship between strategic planning and organizational performance in non government organizations

The r value between organizational performance change and strategic planning process is 0.388, which is more than 0.3. Thus there is an association. $R^2 = 0.151$. This means 15.1% of the variation in O.P. is explained by S.P.P.

Table 4:182: Model Summary of Simple linear regression for S.P.P

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.388 ^a	.151	.149	.54579

a. Predictors: (Constant), s.p.p.2

Table 4:182: Model Summary of Simple linear regression for S.P.P

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.388 ^a	.151	.149	.54579

a. Predictors: (Constant), s.p.p.2

b. Dependent Variable: o.p.e

The p-value is less than 0.001. This means S.P.P can be used to predict O.P.E. Based on the ANOVA table for the linear regression $F(1, 473) = 83.989, p < 0.001$, there was a relationship between the dependent variable "O.P.C" and the independent variable "S.P.P". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected.

The research hypothesis that there was a relationship between the variables was supported.

The regression equation: $O.P.C = 2.395 + 0.352(S.P.P)$. 95% CI for $\beta_1 = [0.277, 0.427]$. For every one unit increase in S.P.P, O.P.C is expected to increase by 0.352 units.

H2: There is a significant relationship between mission achievement and organizational performance in non government organizations

The r value between organizational performance change and M.A is 0.277, which is bellow than 0.3. Thus there is no association.

$R^2 = 0.077$. This means 8% of the variation in O.P.C is explained by M.A. The p-value is less than 0.001. This means M.A can be used to predict O.P.C.

Table 4:186: Analysis of Variances for M.A

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.768	1	12.768	39.434	.000 ^a
	Residual	153.151	473	.324		
	Total	165.919	474			

a. Predictors: (Constant), m.a

b. Dependent Variable: o.p.c

Based on the ANOVA table for the linear regression ($F(1, 473) = 39.434, p < 0.001$), there was a relationship between the dependent variable "O.P.C" and the independent variable "M.A". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected.

The research hypothesis that there was a relationship between the variables was supported.

The regression equation: $O.P.C = 2.718 + 0.279(M.A)$. 95% CI for $\beta_1 = [0.191, 0.366]$. For every one unit increase in M.A, O.P.C is expected to increase by 0.279 units.

H3: There is a significant relationship between customer processes and organizational performance in non government organizations

The r value between organizational performance change and customer perspective is 0.991, which is more than 0.3. Thus there is a strong positive association. $R^2 = 0.981$. This means 98.1% of the variation in O.P.C is explained by C.P. The p-value is less than 0.001. This means C.P can be used to predict O.P.C.

Table 4:189: Analysis of Variances for C.P

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	162.809	1	162.809	24759.962	.000 ^a
	Residual	3.110	473	.007		
	Total	165.919	474			

a. Predictors: (Constant), C.P

b. Dependent Variable: o.p.c

Based on the ANOVA table for the linear regression ($F(1, 473) = 24759.962, p < 0.001$), there was a relationship between the dependent variable "O.P.C" and the independent variable "C.P". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected.

The research hypothesis that there was a relationship between the variables was supported

The regression equation: $O.P.C = 0.036 + 0.982(C.P)$. 95% CI for $\beta_1 = [0.970, 0.995]$. For every one unit increase in C.P, O.P.C is expected to increase by 0.982 units.

H4: There is a significant relationship between internal business processes and organizational performance in non government organizations

The r value between organizational performance change and internal business process perspective is 0.390, which is more than 0.3. Thus there is an association. $R^2 = 0.152$. This means 15.2% of the variation in O.P.C is explained by I.B.P.P. The p-value is less than 0.001. This means I.B.P.P can be used to predict O.P.C.

Table 4:192: Analysis of Variances for I.B.P.P

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	142.247	1	142.247	2842.333	.000 ^a
	Residual	23.672	473	.050		
	Total	165.919	474			

a. Predictors: (Constant), I.B.P.P

b. Dependent Variable: o.p.c

Based on the ANOVA table for the linear regression ($F(1, 473) = 2842.333, p < 0.001$), there was a relationship between the dependent variable "O.P.C" and the independent variable "I.B.P.P". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected.

The research hypothesis that there was a relationship between the variables was supported

The regression equation: $O.P.C = 2.394 + 0.353(I.B.P.P)$. 95% CI for $\beta_1 = [0.278, 0.429]$. For every one unit increase in I.B.P.P, O.P.C is expected to increase by 0.353 units.

H5: There is a significant relationship between employee learning and growth and organizational performance in non government organizations

The r value between organizational performance change and employee learning and growth perspective is 0.905, which is more than 0.3. Thus there is a strong positive association.

$R^2 = 0.819$. This means 81.9% of the variation in O.P.C is explained by E.L.G.P. The p-value is less than 0.001. This means E.L.G.P can be used to predict O.P.C.

Table 4:195: Analysis of Variances for E.L.G.P

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	135.970	1	135.970	2147.458	.000 ^a
	Residual	29.949	473	.063		
	Total	165.919	474			

a. Predictors: (Constant), E.L.G.P

b. Dependent Variable: o.p.c

Based on the ANOVA table for the linear regression ($F(1, 473) = 2147.458, p < 0.001$), there was a relationship between the dependent variable "O.P.C" and the independent variable "E.L.G.P". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected.

The research hypothesis that there was a relationship between the variables was supported

The regression equation: $O.P.C = 0.449 + 0.887(E.L.G.P)$. 95% CI for $\beta_1 = [0.849, 0.924]$. For every one unit increase in E.L.G.P, O.P.C is expected to increase by 0.887 units.

H6: There is a significant relationship between financial processes and organizational performance in non government organizations

The r value between organizational performance change and financial perspective is 0.892, which is more than 0.3. Thus there is a strong positive association. $R^2 = 0.796$. This means 79.6% of the variation in O.P.C is explained by F.P. The p-value is less than 0.001. This means F.P can be used to predict O.P.C

Table 4:198: Analysis of Variances for F.P

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	132.139	1	132.139	1850.224	.000 ^a
	Residual	33.781	473	.071		
	Total	165.919	474			

a. Predictors: (Constant), F.P

b. Dependent Variable: o.p.c

Based on the ANOVA table for the linear regression ($F(1, 473) = 1850.224, p < 0.001$), there was a relationship

between the dependent variable "O.P.C" and the independent variable "F.P". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected.

The research hypothesis that there was a relationship between the variables was supported

The regression equation: $O.P.C = 0.387 + 0.899(F.P)$. 95% CI for $\beta_1 = [0.858, 0.940]$. For every one unit increase in F.P, O.P.C is expected to increase by 0.899 units.

H7: There is a significant relationship between volunteers' development and organizational performance in non government organizations

The r value between organizational performance change and volunteers development perspective is 0.918, which is more than 0.3. Thus there is a strong positive association. $R^2 = 0.842$. This means 84.2% of the variation in O.P.C is explained by V.D.P. The p-value is less than 0.05. This means V.D.P can be used to predict O.P.C.

Table 4:201: Analysis of Variances for V.D.P

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	139.692	1	139.692	2519.363	.000 ^a
	Residual	26.227	473	.055		
	Total	165.919	474			

a. Predictors: (Constant), V.D.P

b. Dependent Variable: o.p.c

Based on the ANOVA table for the linear regression ($F(1, 473) = 2519.363, p < 0.001$), there was a relationship between the dependent variable "O.P.C" and the independent variable "V.D.P". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected.

The research hypothesis that there was a relationship between the variables was supported

The regression equation: $O.P.C = 0.423 + 0.883(V.D.P)$. 95% CI for $\beta_1 = [0.848, 0.918]$. For every one unit increase in V.D.P, O.P.C is expected to increase by 0.883 units.

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1. Main Research Findings

4.1.1. Descriptive Analysis

Based on the results of the descriptive analysis of the investigated non government, it was found that the Sri Lankan non government sector is highly fragmented and many of them provide services in multiple sectors. Majority of them operate mainly in providing Poverty Alleviation, Environment, Health and Sanitation, Protection and Child Rights and Other Services. Female leadership was relatively misrepresented because 66.7% of management executive was represented by men compared to 33.3% of women. Also, there was a lack of youth leadership in the management of these non government, majority of managers were either between 41 and 50 years or 30 and 40 years old. Based on analysis, majority of respondents (54%) indicated their position as the Executive Assistant or Other Officers. Also, majority of respondents spent from 6 to 10 years in tenure in their organizations (32.4%). 31.6% of respondents spent less than 5 years in tenure and they were mostly found in strategic planner organizations and also 28.2% respondents

spent from 11 to 15. This is a good indicator about the adequacy of information reported by respondents based on their accumulated professional experience in the examined organizations. In addition to the categorical data analysis, 68.6% of respondent organizations operate a number of employees less than 25. 18.1% operate within the employee group between 26 -50 and 2.3% operate with a number of employees ranging from 51 to 75 employees.

4.1.2. Assessing the Validity of Scale Items

Factor analysis was used to measure the convergent validity of all research variables. Factor analysis was used to measure the convergent validity of all research variables. A confirmatory factor analysis with one factor extracted was performed on every group of items measuring a single variable. The KMO (Kaiser- Mayer-Olkin) value was used to test the sufficiency of the sample for the confirmatory factor analysis. The principal component extraction method was used to assess the convergent validity of strategic planning process (0.879), mission achievement (0.592), customer perspective (0.699), internal business processes perspective (0.860), employee learning and growth perspective (0.661), financial perspective (0.653), volunteer development perspective (0.671) and organizational performance change (0.766). As a rule of thumb, a KMO value of less than 0.5 is considered poor, a value between 0.5 and 0.6 is considered mediocre, a value between 0.6 and 0.7 is considered acceptable, a value between 0.7 and 0.8 is considered good and a value more than 0.8 is considered excellent. According to the factor analysis the tested values of KMO are within the acceptable level and no one recorded the bellows 0.5 which mean poor. According to the factor analysis, eight variables factor loadings above .5 and thus are considered practically significant (Hair, et al., 1998).

4.1.3. Assessing the Reliability of Scale Items

The reliability analysis shows that Cronbach alpha coefficients for the variables strategic planning process (0.924), mission achievement (0.771), customer perspectives (0.862), internal business process perspectives (0.900), employee learning and growth perspective (0.820), financial perspective (0.794), volunteers' development perspective (0.842) and organizational performance change (0.887) are exceeded .7. Gliem and Gliem (2003) considered Cronbach alpha of greater than or equal .7 as a reasonable indicator of the internal consistency of scale items.

4.1.4. Discriminant Validity Tests

In order to test the discriminant validity of research variables, Cronbach alpha coefficient for each variable will be compared with its correlation with other variables (Sharma and Patterson, 1999). Independent research variables include strategic planning process (S.P.P), mission achievement (M.A), customer perspective (C.P), internal business processes perspective (I.B.P.P), employee learning and growth perspective (E.L.G.P), financial perspective (F.P), and volunteers' development perspective (V.D.P). Thus, the independent variables correlate at an appropriate level as shown by their respective correlation coefficients and at the reported significance levels also they are free from multicollinearity problems. But the I.B.P.P values (0.986) are higher than the reliability value (0.900). Thus these variables are problem with multicollinearity. Also compared the r values between M.A and E.L.G.P, F.P, C.P and V.D.P values are less than 0.3. Thus there is a lower association between the variables and r values between other variables are higher than 0.3. Thus there are strong associations between the variables.

4.1.5. Descriptive summary and inter-item correlation

The highest correlations of each item were between 0.3 and 0.9. Thus there is no convergence problem. The skewness values of all the other items are between ± 1 , thus the criteria of univariate normality can be assumed. But according to the E.L.G.P there is a one question was dropped due to lack of convergence problem and V.D.P dropped two questions under same results were occurred.

Also the skewness values, which is within ± 1 . Hence, data can be assumed to be symmetrical. SPSS provides two methods for testing if the data is distributed normal. The (sample size $n > 60$) can be used when the sample size is large. In either test, if the p value is more than 0.05, normality can be assumed. Hence, the data is distributed not normal ($p < 0.05$) for all supportive variables.

4.2. Hypothesis Testing

4.2.1. Simple Linear regression

H1: There is a positive relationship between strategic planning and organizational performance in non government organizations

The analysis of simple linear regression, r value describe the association between two variables, the value shows 0.388 (higher than the 0.3), which mean there is an association between two variables. As per the Analysis of Variances (ANOVA), p-value is less than 0.001. This means Strategic Planning Process can be used to predict Organizational

Performance Change. Also the significance value in ANOVA ($p < 0.001$), thus it indicated that there was a relationship between the "Organizational Performance Change" and the "Strategic Planning Process". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected and 95% confidence interval for the mean difference does not contain the value of 0. **The research hypothesis that was a relationship between the variable was supported.**

H2: There is a positive relationship between mission achievement and organizational performance in non government organizations

The correlation analysis and r value describe the association between two variables, the value shows 0.277 (lower than the 0.3), which mean there is an association between two variables. As per the Analysis of Variances (ANOVA), p-value is less than 0.001. This means mission achievement can be used to predict Organizational Performance Change. Also the significance value in ANOVA ($p < 0.001$), thus it indicated that there was a relationship between the "Organizational Performance Change" and the "mission achievement". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected and 95% confidence interval for the mean difference does not contain the value of 0. **The research hypothesis that was a relationship between the variables was supported.**

H3: There is a positive relationship between customer processes and organizational performance in government organizations

As per the correlation matrix, r value describes the association between both dependent and independent variables. The P value shows 0.991 (higher than the 0.3), which mean there is an association between two variables. Also the significance value in ANOVA ($p < 0.001$), thus it indicated that there was a relationship between the "Organizational Performance Change" and the "Customer Perspective". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected and 95% confidence interval for the mean difference does not contain the value of 0. **The research hypothesis that was a relationship between the variables was supported.**

H4: There is a positive relationship between internal business processes and organizational performance in non government organizations

The correlation analysis and r value describe the association between two variables, the value shows 0.390 (higher than the 0.3), which mean there is an association between two variables. Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected and 95% confidence interval for the mean difference does not contain the value of 0. The regression equation shows that every one unit increase in Internal Business Process Perspective, **The research hypothesis that was a relationship between the variables was supported.**

H5: There is a positive relationship between employee learning and growth and organizational performance in non government organizations

As per the correlation matrix, r value describes the association between two variables, the value shows 0.905 (higher than the 0.3), which mean there is an association between two variables. Also the significance value in ANOVA ($p < 0.001$), thus it indicated that there was a relationship between the "Organizational Performance Change" and the "Employee Learning and Growth Perspective". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected and 95% confidence interval for the mean difference does not contain the value of 0. **The research hypothesis that was a relationship between the variables was supported.**

H6: There is a positive relationship between financial processes and organizational performance in non government organizations

The correlation analysis and r value describe the association between two variables, the value shows 0.892 (higher than the 0.3), which mean there is an association between two variables. Also the significance value in ANOVA ($p < 0.001$), thus it indicated that there was a relationship between the "Organizational Performance Change" and the "Financial Perspective". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected and 95% confidence interval for the mean difference does not contain the value of 0. The regression equation shows that every one unit increase in Financial Perspective, Organizational Performance Change is expected to increase by 0.899 units. **The research hypothesis that was a relationship between the variables was supported.**

H7: There is a positive relationship between volunteers' development and organizational performance in non government organizations

According to the data analysis r value describe the association between two variables, the value shows 0.918 (higher than the 0.3), which mean there is an association between two variables. This means Financial Perspective can be used to predict Organizational Performance Change. Also the significance value in ANOVA ($p < 0.001$), thus it indicated that there was a relationship between the "Organizational Performance Change" and the "Volunteers Development Perspective". Since the probability of the F statistic ($p < 0.001$) was less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis that correlation coefficient (R) was equal to 0 was rejected and 95% confidence interval for the mean difference does not contain the value of 0. The regression equation shows that every one unit increase in Volunteers Development Perspective, Organizational Performance Change is expected to increase by 0.883 units. **The research hypothesis that was a relationship between the variables was supported.**

4.3. Assumptions and limitations of the research

The proposed research was based on the following assumptions while constrained by some limitations presented hereafter;

4.3.1. Assumptions of the research

1. An objective measurement of the proposed relationships between researches constructs that is independent of the values held by the researcher to avoid the impact of researcher's bias on research results.
2. A moderately diverse sample of Sri Lankan non government organizations will be targeted for two reasons. First: in order to better reflect differences among organizations in these sectors. The differences will be attributed to; the sector in which non government operate, their respective mission and mandates, and the nature of activities performed by each organization. Second: to minimize sample bias, if it is confined to a single sector, and increase potential response rate.
3. The modified balanced scorecard model will be used as an effective means to measuring and comparing performance effectiveness of respondent non government organizations (strategic vs. non strategic planners).

4.3.2. Limitations of the research

1. Scope limitations due to the inability to distinguish the various models of strategic planning used by non government strategic planners and the impact of each model on their performance effectiveness as measured by mission achievement. The study only examined the application of the strategic planning model measured by the survey instrument developed by Blackmon (2008).
2. The difficulties faced by the researcher during the data collection period which has occurred within a very politically intense period and there was a generalized level of fear to submit any information about the civil society organizations working in Sri Lanka. Respondents were very unwilling to supply information about their operating budgets, donors' funding ...etc.
3. Limiting the measurement of performance effectiveness to mission achievement. Other measures of performance effectiveness in the non government sector can include sustainability, market leadership, input-output ratios, and other efficiency indicators.
4. This study was limited to analyzing the data generated through self reports of respondents which might carry a possibility for respondent's bias.
5. Limited Generalizability of research results to the wider non government population in Sri Lanka due of the miss representativeness of the purposive sample included in the research.

4.4. Suggestions for Future Research

Future research can be designed to overcome the limitations encountered in the current the research. The following are some guidelines for further research in the area of strategic management in non government organizations.

1. Future research can examine the primary impediments to utilizing both strategic planning protocol in the management of Sri Lankan non government and the balanced scorecard for performance effectiveness assessment.
2. Further research can examine and analyze the impact of different strategic planning models on improving nonprofits performance effectiveness. Based on this analysis, practical recommendations can be given on what are the strategic planning models that best suit the nature of non government organizations in Sri Lanka.
3. Further research can apply a mixed methods approach for this scientific inquiry. For example, the inquiry can start by a qualitative phase represented by interviewing each stakeholder group (customers, employees, financial executives, board members, and volunteers) respectively, in order to better reflect their own perceptions about and assessment of performance effectiveness of their organizations. This can add more insights on how to further develop

the survey to be used in the second quantitative phase.

4. Further research can investigate the impact of strategic planning on non government organizations' performance effectiveness using multiple indicators of performance effectiveness that are beyond the mere accomplishment of their mission statement.

5. Future research can examine organizational financial performance data to avoid self reporting bias of respondents about their performance effectiveness.

6. Further research can examine the impact of other intervening variables like the quality of management, their level of education, and the number of years in tenure on the correlation between strategic planning and performance effectiveness of non government organizations.

8. Future research on non government organizations needs to question if there is a direct, one to one, causal relationship between non government organizations' performance and strategic planning or other factors might intervene (Griggs, 2002). The only way to measure this is to conduct experimentation and control for the effect of potential extraneous variables.

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